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Effects of seated posture and automotive seat on human thermal response

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Introduction

Efforts to minimise energy expenditure for HVAC in variety of environments (e.g. transportation, working machines, and offices) with help of additional technologies, such as contact heating or ventilation, are nowadays in a centre of research attention. Moreover, well-validated and commercially available thermophysiological models (e.g. [1]) allow simulations of human responses to thermal environments, thus, effectively prompting the research development with a reduced need for human subject studies. On the other hand, the models require precise and detailed inputs, such as clothing thermal properties (clothing area factor, thermal and evaporative resistances), to maintain good predictive accuracy. These data is offered in standards and literature but mostly as global parameters for the entire body, whilst, local clothing properties when seated are scarcely reported. The aim of this study is to develop the methodology for reliable simulations of a human thermo-physiological response, when seated, based on three individual studies: (a) determination of the seat contact area; (b) evaluation of the differences in clothing properties in the standing and seated; (c) demonstration of applicability of a thermophysiological model in spatially heterogeneous conditions using seats with additional conditioning technologies.

Methods

The seat has substantially higher insulating properties compared to indoor clothing. Therefore, it was crucial to specify the contact area involved in the heat exchange. In the first step, a subject study was carried out in a wide range of body weights from normal to overweight (18.5-29.4 kg.m⁻²). The seat contact was examined using a serial production textile covered automotive seat by imprinting a human silhouette to paper covering the seat. Next, the total and local contact areas for seat and back rests were related to simple measures, such as body weight, height, total body area, and BMI. This allowed us to compare the our results to contact area found in literature comprising human studies, full body thermal manikins, a seat tester, and human geometries coupled with thermophysiological models. Lastly, models to predict the contact area based on the human measures were proposed [2].

In the next step, eight cases representing typical scenarios of obtaining clothing properties depend-ing on the equipment level of a given laboratory were studied [3]. However, to demonstrate the differences, we selected only the most advanced (local measurements using western Newton type thermal manikin in seated posture) and the most accessible (estimate based on ISO 9920:2007, Table A.2, no. 114) method to determine clothing properties of indoor winter clothing (T-shirt, turtle neck shirt, jeans, hard soled leather shoes, underwear).

The findings from the previous two studies were applied to the thermophysiological simulations including the effects of the seat heating based on heat flux measurements in the contact area [4]. Simulation outputs were compared to the experimental data from human subject studies. The experimental protocol started with one hour of pre-conditioning in a thermo-neutral environment ($t_{air} = 22 \pm 1$ °C) and was followed by the 30 min chamber exposure in the conditions of $t_{air} = t_{rad} = 18$ °C; $Rh = 50$ %; $v_{air} < 0.2$ m.s⁻¹; metabolic rate of 1.1 met. Both control (10 participants) and exposures with seat heating set to 38 °C (20 participants) were executed. In total, seat contact temperatures (measured on the seat surface), relative humidity, and heat fluxes were recorded separately for back and seat rest. Additional skin temperature measurements at eight locations (based on ISO 9886:2004) were carried out for control seat.

Results and discussion

The results from the first part of the study show an average contact with the seat of 18 % of the total body surface area. Body weight and total body surface area were found as the best predictors for the seat contact area with the coefficient of determination of 0.86 and root mean square deviation of 0.021 m². The comparison of experimental data to literature data revealed differences between the individual approaches. Finally, we confirmed that the contact parts of the virtual human geometry are representative of the human contact area, both in locally and globally.

In the second part of the study, we found substantial differences between the methods to determine the clothing properties. The impact of the differences is demonstrated in Figure 1 A via thermophysiological simulations of the mean skin temperatures using the model by Fiala et al. [1]. The simulations using the clothing properties determined by the Newton show a good match with experimental data, whereas the ISO based clothing results show a systematically higher predicted mean skin temperature of up to 1 K. These differences may have further implications on precision of thermal sensation and comfort predictions. Figure 1 B depicts contact temperatures at buttocks for both control and heated seats that are crucial for local thermal sensation and comfort modelling. Because of the thermal inertia of the seat preconditioned to 18 °C, the contact surface temperatures show a good match with the simulations after approximately the third minute of the exposure.

Figure 1 A – Mean skin temperatures for heated and control seats – simulation based on clothing properties determined by the Newton thermal manikin and ISO 9920:2007; B – Comparison of measured and simulated temperatures at the seat contact using a heat flux boundary condition. Error bars show standard deviation.

Conclusions

The methodology for reliable thermophysiological modelling in seated posture was successfully developed and contributes to research on human comfort in buildings and vehicles.

References

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